

Managing the Frequency Resource Today and Tomorrow

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Introduction

Frequency-resource management is the judicious use of the electromagnetic spectrum to accomplish the mission or objective of the user with little or no impact on other users of the spectrum. One mission of military frequency management is to support command and control (C2), which is crucial to executing the operational plans of the commanders. Effective C2 is impossible without communications and successful communications cannot be achieved without proper frequency management.

This paper does not discuss frequency-management tools in use today, but focuses on factors that must be considered to achieve proper frequency management. The Army of the future must consider not just each radio, but the system into which the radio must fit. "System" refers not to the system of passing messages through a network, but of several radios in proximity, e.g., in mobile command posts (CPs). In such situations, radios designed for individual operations must work in a very dense cosite situation with other types of radios and other equipment such as computers, with radios in several bands together, and radios of various bandwidths.

Managing the electromagnetic spectrum does not begin when radio systems are fielded. It begins with the development community in the selection of the frequency band for a given type of radio, continues with the designers and testers to ensure that the radio does

not adversely impact the electromagnetic environment, and ends with the users operating the radio in accordance with the design goals. Developers, frequency managers, and users must work together to ensure optimum use of the available resources.

The system engineer, who will combine several radio types into one package to fulfill a user requirement, is also part of the frequency-management process. How many antennas can be placed close together, what is the coupling between antennas on the vehicle, what is the impact on the radiation pattern of the antenna from the other antennas and the vehicle, how well were the pieces that constitute the assemblage installed (e.g., properly grounded) are all questions that can affect frequency management.

The design of any radio must reflect a very dense electromagnetic environment; no radio design can ignore the possibility that the radio may be used in a system with other radio types. Thus, the imposition of stringent electromagnetic interference (EMI) standards is required, and every attempt must be made to meet them.

Allocation Tables

Many factors affect frequency-resource management, including international agreements on the use of the spectrum, national implementation of those agreements, operational applications of radio technology, sufficiency of frequencies for training or operations, and proper coordination among the users of spectrum.

Frequency-resource management is much more than mere "bean-counting." To decide what communica-

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tions systems are required for future mission requirements, realistic estimates of the frequency band to be used are required. Historically, the use of various portions of the band evolved as technology evolved. Many of the current frequency-allocation table entries reflect this—they keep moving higher and adding portions for radios, radar, satellites, broadcast, radionavigation, etc.

If the electromagnetic environment has been properly defined and the design engineers meet the requirements, the system will more likely fulfill its mission.

Frequency Allotments and Assignments

Even with proper protection built into the design process, the frequency-assignment process will remain a challenge. Frequency availability is, and will continue to be, a problem in some locations. As the civilian demand for spectrum-dependent services increases, the military must learn to live with less. As various forces are combined to form a fighting force, communication planners and frequency assigners must be aware of the various system and equipment requirements for frequencies. Again, how well was it designed? Were the transmitter signals sufficiently suppressed? Did the receiver adequately reject unwanted signals? Was the signal-processing circuitry designed for the dynamics of communications on the move? Sufficient suppression of transmitter signals, adequate rejection of unwanted signals, and signal-processing circuitry designed for the dynamics of communications on the move are all issues that impact frequency management.

Another impact of the increasing civilian demand on the spectrum is that the military can no longer claim exclusive use of frequency bands. Changes being made to the table of allocations will adversely affect the military's ability to train and operate. Some bands that have historically been military are being transitioned and some new civilian technology will attract the attention of the military. Whether the frequency-management community will "permit" the military to use and operate new systems in the new "civil" bands will need to be determined.

Once the issues of frequency band selection, EMI requirements definition, equipment design and testing, system engineering, installation and use, frequency-

resource requirements definition, and availability have been resolved the frequency assigners can perform their work. If all goes well, there is no problem. If interference occurs, it must be fixed. The frequency assigner, working with the user and the communication system planner, must have the necessary tools and knowledge to effect the necessary fixes.

Various tools and software packages that are available or under development need to be defined. Such software as the Revised Battlefield Electronics Communications-Electronics Operating Instructions (CEOI) System (RBECS), Frequency Assignment System (FAS)-HF, and the Network Planning Terminal (NPT) are currently available. Integrated System Control (ISYSCON) will merge these with other communication planning and management tools in the near future. Improving the spectrum efficiency and use of military radio systems is an ongoing, evolutionary process in a very difficult electromagnetic environment. Modeling and simulation tools to assist in equipment and system design and user planning are being developed. Frequency-resource management is not the last line of action. It must be part of the overall design and planning effort.

The Future

The Army is developing new communication concepts to support tactical concepts that call for highly mobile wideband radios capable of relaying large amounts of data over links that may be line of sight, unmanned aerial vehicle relay, or satellites. The communications systems carried by individual soldiers will have various bandwidths capable of passing either digitized voice or digitized video, which will then be passed to CPs or perhaps further. These radio systems will be combined in a tactical asynchronous transfer mode (ATM) switch operating at over 150 Mbps. These new individual radio systems could be militarized versions of personal communications subsystem devices. The combiner, called a radio access point (RAP), would require a wideband radio link that can be connected to a relay system. There may be several RAPs in the same geographical area, creating the potential for serious frequency-management problems. Perhaps the CPs will contain several vehicles requiring wideband radio links to replace the current cable connections. These mobile CPs may even need to communicate while on the move.

Such future tactical communications concepts will require careful frequency-band selection. As future ATM links will be full-duplex, many MHz of separation will be needed. Careful attention to EMI and electromagnetic compatibility issues will also be necessary to preclude interference as vehicles will have radios with many bands. Antennas will need to be very narrow-beam with well-controlled and suppressed side and rear lobes. It must also be determined if the RAP will require on-board frequency-selection assistance. The future will certainly challenge current concepts of frequency-allocation and network frequency assignment concepts.